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FOREIGN EXPERIENCE OF INCREASING THE EXPORT CAPACITY OF THE REGION AND SPECIFIC FEATURES OF ITS APPLICATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article analyzes the foreign experience of increasing the region's export potential and the features of its application in the case of Surkhandarya region. The study comparatively studied the export development models of South Korea, Germany, Singapore and China. Based on statistical data, the dynamics of the region's foreign trade, export structure and geographical directions were assessed. The results showed that in 2025, the export volume reached 507.5 million US dollars, and vegetable and fruit products were the leaders in the product structure. Based on foreign experience, institutional support, logistics infrastructure and a cluster approach were identified as important factors.

Keywords: export potential, diversification, cluster, logistics, Surkhandarya, foreign trade

INTRODUCTION

The level of integration of regional economies into international trade has become one of the important factors determining regional competitiveness indicators in the global economic space. Export potential, as a comprehensive concept combining the resource base, production capacity, institutional infrastructure and human capital efficiency of the region, acts as an internal source of economic growth. Systematic economic reforms in Uzbekistan, which began in 2017, have raised the task of expanding export activities in the regions, eliminating administrative barriers to access to foreign markets, and diversifying the economy at the regional level.

Surkhandarya region, as a southern border region of Uzbekistan, provides direct access to the markets of Central and South Asia. The agro-climatic potential of the region, mineral resources, and the presence of the Termez international logistics center have created the basis for a significant expansion of its foreign trade turnover. According to official statistics, the region's foreign trade turnover increased from 309.0 million US dollars in 2010 to 790.9 million US dollars in January-December 2025 [1].

The purpose of the article is to summarize the experience of countries that have successfully implemented an export-oriented economic growth model and to identify the specific aspects of using this experience in the case of Surkhandarya region. The task was solved through theoretical generalization, comparative analysis, and statistical research methods.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The central core of the scientific literature on increasing export potential is M. Porter's cluster theory. The scientist justified the formation of competitive advantages through specialized clusters at the regional level, and this approach has found practical confirmation in the experiences of South Korea, Germany, and Singapore [2]. P. Krugman's new trade theory, showing the effects of product diversification and economies of scale, revealed the possibility of specialization in exports for small regions [3].

The annual reports of the World Trade Organization have detailed the role of international trade as a catalyst for growth for developing economies [4]. UNCTAD analyses have highlighted strategies for increasing the share of foreign trade in value added chains in developing countries [5]. The concept of "Trade in Value Added" developed by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development has provided a methodological framework for measuring the degree of integration of regional economies into global production networks [6].

South Korea's export-oriented development model is reflected in the work of KOTRA, which has created a comprehensive service system to support small and medium-sized enterprises in entering foreign markets [7]. In Germany, GTAI is coordinating the linkage of interregional export centers and industrial clusters with international trade [8]. Singapore's EDB has provided a successful example of public-private partnership in promoting high-tech exports and trade in services [9].

The research of local economists has devoted a lot of attention to the issues of export orientation of the economy of Uzbekistan's regions. Foreign trade balances published by the State Statistics Committee form the empirical basis for the analysis of regional exports [10]. The Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022, identified increasing regional export potential as a separate priority area [11]. The ITC Trade Map database provides modern analytical tools for detailed analysis of the interregional export commodity nomenclature [12].

An analysis of scientific sources revealed the need for a multidisciplinary approach: increasing the region's export potential is based on the balance of structural elements such as the resource base, institutional environment, logistics, and human capital.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research was carried out on the basis of a systematic approach and combined the following methods: theoretical generalization, comparative analysis, statistical observation, and dynamic series analysis. The database used was official publications of the Surkhandarya regional statistics department, annual reports of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and open data from international organizations.

At the comparative analysis stage, the experiences of South Korea, Germany, Singapore and China were compared in terms of four main criteria - institutional support, financing mechanisms, infrastructure development and human capital. The statistical analysis studied the dynamics of foreign trade of Surkhandarya region in 2010-2025, classified the export-import structure by commodity and country. When assessing regional export potential indicators, the ratio of the region's foreign trade turnover to gross regional product was taken into account. Data for 2025 were preliminary data published by the official statistics department for the period January-December, and indicators for 2026 were for the period January-March [1].

To ensure the reliability of the analysis results, data from several official sources were cross-referenced and statistical stability was checked.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The dynamics of foreign trade in Surkhandarya region has shown a steady growth trend over the past fifteen years. Foreign trade turnover, which amounted to 309.0 million US dollars in 2010, reached 589.1 million in 2018, 424.8 million in 2024, and 790.9 million US dollars in January-December 2025 [1]. A significant expansion of export indicators was observed in 2025: the region's exports reached 507.5 million US dollars, recording an increase of 186.2 percent compared to the previous year. Such a positive trend is assessed as a result of the deeper integration of the regional industry into the value chain and the expansion of foreign market partners.

Vegetables and fruits occupy a leading position in the export structure, in 2025 this group amounted to 200.5 million US dollars and covered 39.5 percent of the region's exports [1]. Textile products amounted to 37.4 million US dollars, and the process of transition from raw silk to finished fabrics and knitted products continues in the value chain. Gold exports have emerged as a new structural element, reaching 99.0 million US dollars in 2025. The emergence of gold exports reflected the expansion of the region's industry into new areas (Table 1).

Table 1.

Leading export goods and partner countries of Surkhandarya region in 2024-2025, million US dollars[1]

No.	Product group / Partner country	2024, million US dollars	2025, million US dollars	Share in exports in 2025, in percent
Leading export commodity groups				
1	Vegetables and fruits	161.5	200.5	39.5
2	Gold (non-monetary)	-	99.1	19.5
3	Textile products (fabric and yarn)	49.9	37.4	7.4

4	Cereal crops and products made from them	15.0	24.0	4.7
5	Oilseeds and fruits	11.0	6.6	1.3
Leading export partner countries				
6	United Arab Emirates	0.1	200.9	39.6
7	Afghanistan	43.0	132.7	26.1
8	Pakistan	57.5	64.3	12.7
9	Russian Federation	102.0	62.1	12.2
10	Kazakhstan	14.5	9.5	1.9

In terms of geographical diversification, the region’s exports were mainly directed to five major markets. In 2025, the United Arab Emirates became the leading partner with exports worth 200.9 million US dollars, Afghanistan with 132.7 million US dollars, Pakistan with 64.3 million US dollars, the Russian Federation with 62.1 million US dollars, and Kazakhstan with 9.5 million US dollars [1]. This distribution reflects the advantages of the region’s geographical location and the transportation chain of wholesale goods.

The dynamics of gross regional product expanded in parallel with the growth of foreign trade. The GRP of Surkhandarya region increased from 3,394.7 billion soums in 2010 to 66,186.5 billion soums in 2025 [1]. Although agriculture retained its leadership in the sector, the share of industry increased from 6.7 percent in 2010 to 9.9 percent in 2025. Investment activity reached 22,758.4 billion soums in 2025, thirty-four times higher than in 2010 [1] (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Structural model of regional export potential¹

Comparing the experience of foreign countries with the conditions of the Surkhandarya region yielded the following results. The model of a state agency for the export of small and medium-sized enterprises from the experience of South Korea, the concept of regional export clusters from the experience of Germany, the system of logistics and trade platforms from the experience of Singapore, and the mechanism of export-oriented economic zones from the experience of China stood out as suitable approaches for adaptation to the conditions of the region.

The analysis showed that the region’s export potential can be expanded in three main areas: first, increasing added value through deep processing of agricultural products; second, producing finished products

1 Compiled by the author based on a literature analysis.

together with international brands through a textile cluster; and third, developing the export of transit and logistics services through the Termez International Trade Center.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The study showed that Surkhandarya region has entered a phase of significant expansion of its export potential. The export figure of 507.5 million US dollars in 2025 reflected a significant positive trend compared to previous years and indicates the strengthening of the region's role in foreign economic relations.

Analysis of the experience of foreign countries made it possible to formulate the following proposals in the regional context:

Establish a regional export agency - based on the South Korean KOTRA model, it is advisable to create a structure at the regional level that coordinates market analysis, certification, and liaison services for small businesses with foreign participants;

Deepening the cluster approach to fruit and vegetable exports - building specialized export clusters in the Surkhandarya region for pomegranate, grape, and citrus products, based on the experience of Germany, can yield effective results;

Increasing the capacity of the Termez International Logistics Center - creating a modern infrastructure for transit trade and re-export services based on the experience of Singapore - will open up a new direction for the region's export potential;

activation of small export-oriented economic zones - based on the experience of China, it is necessary to improve the special tax and customs regime for free economic zones located in the region;

human capital development - the introduction of advanced training programs in export management, international trade law, and digital marketing will increase the effectiveness of export policy at the regional level;

Diversification of markets - expanding the geography of exports by entering the markets of the European Union and Southeast Asia will ensure the stability of the region's foreign trade.

These areas of improvement of regional export policy have created new opportunities for sustainable economic growth and improving the living standards of the population of Surkhandarya region. The results obtained have practical significance for use in strategic planning at the regional level and in improving export potential assessment methodologies.

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